

INTELLIGENT AUTOMOTIVE NETWORK APPLICATIONS

Newsletter November 2024

INSIDE THIS ISSUE

- 1 Summary
- 2 5G-IANA Open Call #2
- 3 5G-IANA Final Event
- 4 www.5g-iana.eu
- 5 5G-IANA project news
- 6 Project Events

5G-IANA: a Horizon 2020 project on 5G Intelligent Automotive Network Applications aiming at providing an open 5G experimentation platform, on top of which third party experimenters, i.e., Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the Automotive-related 5G-PPP vertical will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services.

Download the flyer to see all the information about 5G-IANA at a glance

1 The eighth issue of 5G-IANA Newsletter summarises 5G-IANA's activities from April 2024 to October 2024.

This issue puts the focus on 5G-IANA's final event.

The 5G-IANA platform has been continuously enriched with new features, demonstrating its capability to support innovative solutions. We are excited to present these developments and highlight the significant impact the project has had on the 5G and automotive ecosystem. In that context, and over the past few months since April, the 5G-IANA project has been working intensively to prepare for the **final event on October 23, 2024**. Hosted at **Telekom Slovenia**, this event showcased the project's key achievements through live demos and provide an opportunity to explore cutting-edge technology in action. Attendees also had the chance to engage with **real-time talks and interviews**, gaining insights from project experts, alongside the presence of Telecom Slovenia with the Vice-President of the Management Board opening the event, and local Slovenian VIPs from the **Administration for Civil Protection and Disaster Relief**.

This issue also summarises the communication and dissemination activities addressed during this seven-month period.

OPEN CALL #2

Open Call has been closed!

2

5G-IANA's second Open Call has been closed!

As it was announced, the call was awarded on a First Come, First Served basis, therefore our coach-committee assessed all the proposals as they arrived and evaluated their viability in order to choose the winners.

The experiments have already been finished, and you can see all of them in our YouTube channel!

Final Event

5G-IANA

3

5G-IANA is coming to an end, and we have reached one relevant milestone: our final event!

The 5G-IANA: 5G Intelligent Automotive Network Applications Final Event took place on October 23rd, 2024, in Ljubljana, Slovenia, hosted by Telekom Slovenije. The event featured keynote addresses from the EU Project Officer, Dr. Jorge Pereira, alongside prominent Slovenian VIPs, and expert-led demonstrations of pioneering 5G innovations in the automotive sector. Attendees gained valuable insights into the project's objectives and practical applications, with ample opportunities to network with industry leaders and innovators. The event's highlight was live demonstrations of advanced applications, including cross-border road tunnel accident awareness, AI-powered remote driving, and autonomous vehicle coordination, providing an exclusive preview of the future of intelligent automotive technologies.

Thank you to Telekom Slovenia for hosting such a wonderful event, to all the people involved, and of course, to all the participants!

5g-iana.eu

4 Learn more about our Success Stories!

In our **new section**, you will be able to find a brief description of the use cases, as well as an interview about each of them!

USE CASE 5 - High-risk driving hotspot detection

Use Case 5 aims to develop a feature that will be integrated in the 5G-IANA platform, which will detect aggressive and distracted driving (hazardous events), and transmit warning notifications on road risk-level to other vehicles.

You can hear an interview to the Use Case 5 leader in the following video:

And keep browsing www.5g-iana.eu, we have new features...

5G-IANA project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016427.

The 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership

5G-IANA PROJECT NEWS

5 Consortium meeting

Consortium meeting

The 5G-IANA consortium travelled to Ljubljana, Slovenia, in July for a review meeting kindly hosted by Telecom Slovenia. We all enjoyed seeing each other again, several demos were presented and it was a very fruitful meeting.

ICT-41 plugfest report

The ICT-41 PlugFest 2023 took place on October 23-24, 2023 in Aveiro (Portugal), and was a very useful event that 5G-IANA used to continue working on some experiments, demonstrating the seamless interoperability between the ICT-41 projects' network applications and the 5G-IANA platform, and vice versa. Our report about interoperability is available [here!](#)

COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

6 Events attended:

EuCNC 2024

was held in Antwerp, Belgium, between June 3rd and 6th. 5G-IANA organised a Special session on Automotive/CAM.

14th Mobile & IoT Connected World

took place in Athens, Greece, on June 26th, in which 5G-IANA was presented. Moreover, our colleagues from INCITES participated in the Panel Discussion regarding Development of 5G applications in the automotive sector by new companies.

IEEE International Conference on High Performance Switching and Routing in Pisa, Italy

on 22th-24th July, in which a joint demo was presented by our partners NXT and LINKS.

Pre-Standardisation WG

On 16th October, the project 5G-IANA was presented in the 6G-IA Pre-Standardisation WG by our colleagues in FSCOM.

COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

IEEE VTC in Washington

Under the "Network Applications" session, ICCS represented the 5G-IANA project. They showcased the 5G Open Experimentation platform, the innovative Network Applications, and the synergetic use cases developed by our project.

5G-IANA PROJECT EVENTS

7 Events organised by 5G-IANA:

Finishing our series of webinars, our last webinar will be held:

5G-IANA open calls' results and feedback: Lessons learnt from start-ups' and SMEs' integration. Sustainability-related aspects so that platform exploitation is incentivised even after the end of the project. This webinar will be held on 21st November at 11. Stay tuned for more information and registration!

Our webinar about Business Models was successfully held on October 30th

The webinar began with an overview of the 5G-IANA platform. Different scenarios for the service creation and provision showing the different roles that actors can take within the ecosystem were presented considering the ecosystem around the 5G-IANA experimentation platform. The possible business model for the exploitation of the 5G-IANA platform was presented. Finally, the success story of Use Cases were presented highlighting the benefits of 5G-IANA platform and the possible exploitation paths

5G-IANA PROJECT EVENTS

7,1 Publication

6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association

Smart city trials in Europe – Summary of activities in smart city vertical segments/use cases

6G-IA REPORT

*SMART CITY TRIALS IN EUROPE – SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES
IN SMART CITY VERTICAL SEGMENTS/USE CASES*

Development & Reliable Orchestration of Network Applications for the Automotive Domain Across the Edge-to-Cloud Continuum

Gabriele Scivoletto¹, Matteo Andolfi², Eirini Liotou³, Konstantinos V. Katsaros⁴, Federico Princiotta⁵,
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Development & Reliable Orchestration of Network Applications for the Automotive Domain

*Across the Edge-To-Cloud Continuum, Gabriele Scivoletto,
Matteo Andolfi, Eirini Liotou, Konstantinos V. Katsaros,
Federico Princiotta, Edoardo Bonetto, Daniele Brevi,
Thanos Xirofotou, Giada Landi, Manuel Fuentes and
Miriam Ortiz, Robert Horvath, Markus Wimmer; EuCNC &
6G Summit conference proceedings.*

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